

A STUDY OF INNOVATIONS ISSUES AND PROBLEMS OF TEACHER EDUCATION IN SOLAPUR

Shri.Gajendra Tukaram Jamadar

Assistant Professor

Solapur University, Solapur

The objectives of the study were: (1) To evaluate the present method and procedure of admission in the teacher's training institutions in solapur. (2) To determine whether the present curriculum of teacher education is relevant to the new roles and responsibilities of teachers or not. (3) To find out whether the various functional aspects of training are covered and the duration of the training is sufficient or not. (4) To find out whether the teachers training colleges in Solapur are practicing innovative methods for better learning and higher achievement or not and to evaluate the effectiveness of these innovations. (5) To find out the physical facilities available in training institutions and also their suitability for the program. (6) To throw light on the process of recruitment of teacher educators, their minimum qualifications and their relevance for the work they do. (7) To find out the level of interaction between the teacher education programs and community participation. (8) To ascertain the type and level of research training in training colleges. (9) To find out the relationship between pre-service and in-service teacher education in the solapur.

The study was descriptive type survey research. Sample comprised of 40 teacher educators of DIET, 20 teacher-trainees and 05 experts of DIET, training college, PG Departments of Education. Stratified random sampling and multi stage random sampling techniques were used. A questionnaire related to admission, curriculum infrastructure, qualification and orientation of teacher educators, innovations in teacher-education, issues in teacher education, problems in teacher educator community training relationship and research in teacher education and an interview schedule constructed by investigator were used for collecting the data. Percentage and central tendency were used for data analysis.

The findings of the study were: (1) Direct admission should be discouraged. Entrance test, interview and marks of the last qualifying examinations should be the criteria for the admission to the teacher education programs. Certain percentage of seats should be reserved for candidates excelling in sports and music so that the students in school can benefit from

such student trainees who will become teacher later. (2) Correct training in theory, skills, practice teaching etc. is quite essential which will result in bringing about a commitment towards the learner, the society and his profession. The curriculum is useful as per 71% of the population. However, it can be improved further to make it more useful and effective. (3) The curriculum is not sufficient. It must be associated with society; it should be gender sensitive to achieve the goal of universalization of education. The curriculum is vast for the year session. (4) SUPW and other activities are only 72%. 61% training institutes train their students in doing research projects; 59.6% training institute only encouraging micro-teaching; only 59.6% institute have their students undergoing actual and rigorous practice teaching while many of them have it on paper only; value education and value-orientation is absent in curriculum. (5) Only 54.4% institute have well equipped laboratory; 90.2% have a library, 805 of them only have sufficient number of books; 76.8% institutes have project room; 85.4% institutes show students interest to willing and volunteering to participation in seminars. (6) 84.4% of the data reveal that almost all subject teachers are available; teacher educators are recruited by the government in 27.8% cases; 51.8% teacher educators undergo in-service training or orientation program. The teacher educators are very professional, keen to update and enrich their knowledge and skill; in-service training is useful and very effective bringing out a qualitative change in the teacher educators. (7) 59.5% from the data show the use of the latest method of teaching. The art of interaction has to be taught and projected in student teachers to create a rapport with the pupils and simultaneously build the unit being taught; evaluation is continuous and comprehensive using a lot of new techniques and skills; 55% positive reply shows that more efforts are needed in conducting simulation exercises result in observation and feedback immediately; observation of result is at 56% and feedback at 62.89%; skills are being improved partially at 68.1% in the training program; 59.6% population are aware of microteaching and its benefits; action research is not given much importance (35%). (8) Tackling of issues and awareness of them should be part of the training program. They include the following: (a) social issues, like, child rights and labor, children of underprivileged group, women empowerment, local verses global community, and children of special needs. (b) Economic issues, like, liberal economy and education and economic development etc. (c) cultural issues, like, value crisis, secularism, modernity. (d) political issues, like, education as a fundamental right, fundamental duties, Panchyati Raj, community ownership. (e) curricular issues, like, skill development, TLM, community resource and evaluation examination etc. (9) Lack of proper building, rooms for each subjects, adequate library, well equipped laboratory, drinking water are the basic amenities,

salary on time to staff, wrong process of admission, lack of practicing schools; the imbalance in the teacher-student ratio, non-availability of teachers in every subject; qualification of teacher educators; out dated curriculum, monotonous and routine methods of teaching; music room, growth of colleges of education, correspondence courses, detachment of community etc, are some the major problems of teacher education institutes.

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